

Effects of Environmental Pollution in Liberia: A Case Study of Montserrado (Republic of Liberia)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Environmental pollution is not a discovery; it continues to present as the greatest problem that humanity faces and the leading factor contributing to morbidity and mortality (Ukaogo et al., 2020) and is a wide-reaching predicament that is likely to influence human and population health (Khan & Ghouri, 2011). **Methodology:** The quantitative research design was used to investigate the effects of environmental pollution because it provides statistical evidence of the impact of environmental pollution. The research considers the 2022 National census report of Montserrado County at, a population of 1,920,914, using the Slovincs formula to derive the sample size 400. However, during the data collection, the researcher collected data from an additional five (5) persons, increasing the sample size to 405. This was considered because the larger the sample size, the more accurate the research findings, as the CI of 95% was considered. The data was collected using Google Forms, while the SPSS was used to analyze the collected data. **Findings:** The data shows that people living in poverty and children are the most vulnerable population to the effects of environmental pollution. Moreover, the study also indicates that increased health expenses are a major economic impact of environmental pollution. **Key Recommendation:** The study recommends public-private partnerships and the use of eco-friendly products.

Keywords: Environment, Effects, Pollution, Strategies

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution is reaching worrying proportions worldwide. Urbanization, industrialization, and economic growth have increased energy consumption and waste discharges. Greenhouse gas emissions and acid deposition, including water pollution and waste management, are globally considered to be of public health significance (Kelishadi, 2012). Clean air is an essential human right and an important element of public health and environmental sustainability. In 2017, charcoal consumption in the residential sector contributed 48% of total black carbon emissions in Liberia, followed by residential wood consumption, which contributed 34%. In the commercial sector, charcoal consumption contributed 3% to the total black carbon emissions. Wood combustion in food production contributed to 7% of total national emissions in the industrial sector (Gomah, 2024). Environmental pollution has several adverse health effects, including infant mortality,

respiratory disorders, perinatal disorders, an increase in oxidative stress, mental disorders, and cardiovascular disorders (Rahman et al., 2021). Non-communicable diseases continue to increase in Sub-Saharan Africa due to environmental conditions such as heavy metals and air pollution, which have been linked with the incidence and mortality of chronic diseases, including cancer and cardiovascular diseases (Anyanwu et al., 2024). However, managing environmental pollution is still a significant challenge in Liberia. Investigating the effects of environmental pollution in Liberia is a significant emergency.

BACKGROUND:

Environmental pollution is not a discovery; it continues to present as the greatest problem that humanity faces and the leading factor contributing to morbidity and mortality (Ukaogo et al., 2020) and is a wide-reaching predicament that is likely to influence human and population health (Khan & Ghouri, 2011).

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Environmental pollution is an undesirable modification in the biological, physical, and chemical characteristics of water, air, and land that may harmfully affect human life or any other desirable species, industrial processes, living conditions, or cultural assets. Man's quest to build the environment and the increased scale of human activity has laid the basis for pollution (Singer, 1970). Contacts to environmental pollution remain a major source of health risk globally. Developing countries pose a higher risk due to weak environmental legislation, lack of investment in modern technology, and poverty, which increase pollution levels (Briggs, 2003a). According to Zandalinas et al. (2021), Climate change, global warming, and industrial pollution could increase the frequency, intensity, and complexity of multifactorial stress combinations impacting soils, plants, and microbial communities (Zandalinas et al. 2021). The effects of pollution in developing countries cannot be overemphasized, as it has taken on a worldwide dimension. Currently, pollution is restricted to humans and has long-term effects on the soil, vegetation, and animals. This statement has created the urgency for awareness among the cross-section of society of the hazards posed by pollution and a need for the all-inclusive development and enforcement of appropriate policies to prevent it (Babayemi et al., 2016). Inappropriate waste management is increasing daily in Liberia due to a shortage of inclusive frameworks for waste management. The absence of guidelines detailing the responsibilities of those generating waste and the limitation of the decision maker's intention to design and implement integrated systems to manage waste sustainably is exacerbating the already inflamed situation (David et al., 2020a). Liberia is a developing country that is faced with significant challenges in its energy sector, with limited access to electricity and substantial reliance on traditional biomass. In 2019+, Liberia had access to 3% of electricity and was among the lowest globally. Traditional biomass use poses indoor air pollution risks, especially for women and children (Yusuf et al., 2024). Out-of-door air pollution is an essential contributor to indoor air pollution. A complex mixture of solid particles called particulate air pollution and liquid droplets is found in the air. The particles can originate from different sources like smoke stacks, diesel exhaust, and construction, causing inflammatory effects both

locally and on the body (Redlich, et al., 2023) Recently, several attempts have been made to assess the burden of diseases caused by environmental pollution, either in terms of disability-adjusted life or mortality. However, it is estimated that 8-9% of the total universal disease burden may be attributed to pollution, but considerably more so in developing countries with poor sanitation, unsafe water, and poor hygiene practices (Briggs, 2003b). According to the United Nations Environment Programme (2025), Environmental contamination adversely contributes to non-infectious diseases like cancer and respiratory illnesses, causing approximately nine million deaths annually. It is essential to know that air pollution alone is responsible for nearly seven million deaths (Environment, 2024). Soil pollution is a major and developing threat to human health due to its vulnerability to being polluted by organic chemicals and heavy metals. It supports critical ecological services and diverse ecosystems. Moreover, it stores water, prevents floods, captures carbon, and slows global climate change. We need healthy soil to grow crops for food consumption to sustain the growing population, which is fundamental to human and animal health (Münzel et al., 2022). Indoor air pollution accounts for approximately 3.8 million inopportune deaths annually globally. Due to spending more time indoors, children and older adults are mainly susceptible to the health risks of indoor air pollution (Ndlovu & Nkeh-Chungag, 2024). The impact of mortality-risk classification on various healthcare expenditures is significant (Li et al., 2020). According to the "State of the Air" (2024) report, 39% of the people living in America, approximately 131.2 million people, still live in places with failing grades for unhealthy ozone or particle pollution levels. This report shows an additional 11.7 million people breathing unhealthy air compared to the 2023 reports (ALA, 2024). Solid waste management protocols and system dynamic modelling support policy development as it use waste prevention to explain the complex waste management systems and suggests methods for effective management. However, creating an effective waste system goes beyond formulating policies and legislation (David et al., 2020b). Liberia faces enormous challenges and growing anxieties regarding the inadequacies of its waste management activities (ICAT, 2002). As a result, investigating the effects of environmental

pollution and implementing strategies to mitigate its impact is an urgent priority for the country. This background raises lots of questions that need to be addressed. Paramount amongst those questions include examining the economic consequences of environmental pollution, identifying the vulnerable populations most affected by environmental pollution, the causes of the effects, and helping minimize the effects.

General Objective:

This research aims to address the effects of environmental pollution on public health in Liberia. Specifically, the research will consider:

1. Examining the economic consequences of environmental pollution
2. Identifying the vulnerable populations most affected by environmental pollution, including children, older people, and those living in poverty
3. Recommending ways to minimize the effects of environmental pollution

REVIEW OF EXISTING LITERATURE

Economic consequences of environmental pollution

Air pollution is a persistent environmental issue that significantly impacts public health and ecology. It can also cause long-term damage to economic growth, development, and human welfare. Since the effects of air pollution on the economy are multifaceted, they can substantially damage productivity and decrease quality of life (Airly, 2025). There is a cross-disciplinary link between the climate change crisis, air pollution, and sustainable lifestyle, as they are the most complex struggles of this 21st century (Afifa et al., 2024). The twenty-first century realized the corporate world that environmental stability is an important factor for sustainable growth (Bari et al., 2022). Environmental procedures raise production costs at controlled levels where, at times, case costs are just a small proportion of the firm's total costs (Gray, 2015) One of the major effects of environmental pollution history is the Deep-Water Horizon oil spill in the United States, which was of national importance in the United States history and

significantly impacted the health of Gulf of Mexico communities (Sandifer et al., 2021).

The population is affected mainly by environmental factors.

Children, older adults, and the poor are globally vulnerable to environmental pollution (Sheffield & Landrigan, 2011). Education and awareness are important in addressing the impact of environmental pollution on population health (Ramírez et al., 2019). Environmental supremacy is related to the healthy living average of human beings and the sustainable development of an economic society (Vogel et al., 2021). It is of great significance to explore the inspiration of government trust and environmental pollution perception on environmental governance satisfaction to improve the performance of government environmental governance (Ruan et al., 2022) According to Rentschler and Leonova (2023), 7.3 billion people face air pollution levels that are considered unsafe globally by the World Health Organization, increasing mortality rates by 4 percent compared to safe areas. 6.2 billion are directly exposed to at least moderate air pollution levels, which increases mortality risk by 8 percent, and 2.8 billion are exposed to hazardous pollution levels, which increases mortality risk by 24 percent (Rentschler & Leonova, 2023a). All age groups are affected by pollution in Liberia, but women are disproportionately affected for many reasons. People who rely on the rivers in Liberia adversely suffer whenever the rivers and water bodies are polluted (Nigba, 2023). About 70% of women are among the people in poverty. This implies that women are more vulnerable to the effects of climate change than men. Women in developing countries are usually responsible for collecting food, fuel, and water. This is because climate change affects the accessibility of resources (Blake, 2024)

Reducing the effects of environmental pollution

Preventing pollution is reducing, eliminating, or controlling it before it forms (US EPA, 2013). Reducing pollution is possible; it is being done at an intergovernmental level, for example, with the many climate summits, despite sluggishness and uncertainty (UN, 2024). Addressing various factors, including air pollution in our neighborhoods and homes, can

prevent pollution. Avoiding backyard fires, auto body shops, and emissions from vehicles and construction equipment are among the measures to consider (MPCA, 2022).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The quantitative research was designed to investigate the effects of environmental pollution. The quantitative methods provide statistical evidence on the impact of environmental pollution (College, 2017). We considered the 2022 National Census report, which puts Montserado County at a population of 1,920,914, using Slovinc's formula. When sampling a population, this formula calculates the necessary sample size to achieve a given confidence interval. The researcher uses a confidence level of 95%.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

n is equal to the sample size
 N is equal to the total population and
 e is the margin of error

$$n = \frac{1,920,914}{1 + 1,920,914 \times 0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1,920,914}{1 + 1,920,914 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{1,920,914}{1 + 4802.285}$$

$$n = \frac{1,920,914}{4803.285}$$

$$n = 399.9 \approx 400$$

$$n = 400$$

During the data collection, the researcher collected data from an additional five (5), increasing the sample size to 405. This excess is good because the larger the sample size, the more accurate the research findings. The Google form was used for data collection, while SPSS was used to analyze the data collected.

RESULTS

Table 1: Sex of the Respondents

	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	183	45.2	45.2	45.2
Female	217	53.6	53.6	98.8
Prefer not say	5	1.2	1.2	100.0
Total	405	100.0	100.0	

Field data 2024-2025
 Of four hundred and five respondents, 183 were males, constituting 45.2%, while 217 were females,

constituting 53.6%; however, five persons 1.2% preferred not to disclose their genders.

Figure 1: Age of the Respondents

Field data 2024-2025

One hundred eighty-two of the respondents were in the age range of 26-33, constituting 44.9% of the total respondents, while one hundred fifty-five of the

respondents were in the age range of 34 years and above, also constituting 38.3 % with sixty-eight persons in the age range of 18-25 or 16.8%.

Table 2: Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Single	292	72.1	72.1	72.1
Married	100	24.7	24.7	96.8
Divorced	4	1.0	1.0	97.8
Widow	9	2.2	2.2	100.0
Total	405	100.0	100.0	

The research participants included two hundred ninety-two-person single persons, or 72.1%, hundred

married persons, constituting 24.7%, four divorced persons (1.0%), and nine widows (2.2%)

Table 3: Educational Status of the Respondents

Level of education	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Junior High	17	4.2	4.2	4.2
High School Diploma	78	19.3	19.3	23.5
Some undergraduate degree Courses	118	29.1	29.1	52.6
Associated degree	72	17.8	17.8	70.4
Bachelor degree	67	16.5	16.5	86.9
Some graduate coursed	23	5.7	5.7	92.6
Master degree	30	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	405	100.0	100.0	

Field data 2024-2025

One hundred and eighteen of the participants (29.1%) have undertaken some undergraduate degree courses, seventy-eight persons (19.3%) have high school

diplomas and seventy-two persons (17.8%) have obtained associate degrees. However, the data also shows that sixty-seven (16.5%) and thirty persons have obtained bachelor's and master's degrees, respectively.

Table 4: Employment Status of the Respondents

	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Unemployed	153	37.8	37.8	37.8
Employed	188	46.4	46.4	84.2
Self Employed	64	15.8	15.8	100.0
Total	405	100.0	100.0	

Field data 2024-2025

Table 4 shows that 46.4% of the respondents are employed, and 37.8% are unemployed. The table also

shows that 15.8%, comprising sixty-four participants, are self-employed.

Figure 2: Economic Impact of Environmental Pollution

Field data 2024-2025

Figure 2. Presents 188 persons (46.4%) respondents out of the 405 respondents reporting that an "increase in health expenses" is the major economic impact of

environmental pollution, while 121, constituting 29.9% of the 405 respondents, reported "loss of agricultural productivity" as the leading economic impact of environmental pollution.

Figure 3: Population Vulnerable to Environmental Pollution

Field data 2024-2025

According to Figure 3. Presentation: 219 persons, or 54.07% of 405 respondents, reported that the most vulnerable population to environmental pollution is

those living in poverty. At the same time, 145 persons, or 35.8% of the respondents, ascertained that children are the most vulnerable population to Environmental pollution.

Table 5: Effective strategies for minimizing the effects of environmental pollution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Use eco-friendly(biodegradable) Products	115	28.4	28.4	28.4
Buy energy-efficient appliances	108	26.7	26.7	55.1
Walk whenever possible	21	5.2	5.2	60.3
Be careful not to spill fuel	13	3.2	3.2	63.5

Reduce burning in an uncontrolled manner	73	18.02	18.02	81.52
Stop open defecation	53	13.08	13.08	94.6
Reduce the number of trips you take in a car	22	5.4	5.4	100
	405	100	100	

Field data 2024-2025

Out of the 405 respondents, 115 and 108, constituting 28.4 and 26.7 percent, respectively, of the total

respondents, suggested using eco-friendly products and energy-efficient appliances to minimize the effects of environmental pollution.

Figure 4: Policies to be applied to minimize environmental Pollution in Liberia

Field data 2024-2025

From the data presented in Figure 4. 139 (34.2%) respondents preferred the establishment of a public-private partnership for municipal solid waste, while 123 (30.4%) suggested the implementation of the Liberia Public Health Laws.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

➤ The economic impact of environmental pollution

Figure 2 shows an increase in health expenses as a major pollution. Secondary is the loss of agricultural productivity. Considering the growing healthcare problem in Liberia, respiratory and digestive conditions are increasing. Health facilities are overwhelmed by the number of cases received in Liberia. According to Yan et al. (2022) in the article "Environmental Pollution and Economic Growth," the growth rates of China's gross domestic product and SO₂ emissions are significant (Yan et al., 2022).

➤ Population vulnerable to environmental pollution

Everyone is vulnerable to environmental pollution. However, some populations are more vulnerable than others. According to Figure 3, 219 respondents (54.07%) reported that the most vulnerable population is those living in poverty and children 35.8%. Children and the elderly are the groups of people who are always vulnerable in society due to their dependency and compromised immune systems. However, people living in poverty are disadvantaged in terms of environmental pollution because of their low socioeconomic status. According to Rentschler and Leonova's (2023) article titled "Global air pollution exposure and poverty, 716 million of the world's lowest-income people live in areas with unsafe levels of air pollution, especially in sub-Saharan Africa (Rentschler & Leonova, 2023b) The findings also aligned with the World Health Organization's (2023) "Environmental health inequalities." Higher environmental exposure levels are primarily associated with socioeconomic deprivation (WHO, 2023).

➤ Effective strategies for minimizing the effects of Environmental pollution

According to Table 5, the use of eco-friendly products and energy-efficient appliances will be effective in minimizing the effects of pollution. From the data shown, 115 and 108, constituting 28.4 and 26.7 percent, respectively, suggested the use of eco-friendly products is that there are less biodegradable materials, which reduces waste in the environment and landfills. At the same time, energy-efficient appliances create job opportunities and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The European Consumer Centre France states, "Eco-friendly products have a lower impact on the environment through their life cycle." However, an Eco-friendly product can also be an ethical product that considers the working conditions in which the product has been designed and distributed (ECC-Net, 2024). According to the US EPA (2017), using energy more efficiently is one of the most cost-effective and fastest ways to save money, create jobs, and meet the growing energy demand (US EPA, 2017). Liberia is one of the sub-Saharan countries with limited access to electricity. With the high energy demand, most of the populace is engaging in solar energy uses, creating jobs for the installer.

➤ Policies to apply to minimize environmental pollution in Liberia

Figure 4 shows that establishing public-private partnerships (PPPs) for municipal solid waste management is key to minimizing environmental pollution, as 139 (34.2%) research respondents indicated. The government in every country cannot do it all, so establishing PPPs will create jobs and make the system more effective. Creating job opportunities will help reduce the number of people living in poverty, as seen in Figure 3. Nevertheless, it is also good to consider the Liberia Public Health laws since they establish the rules and regulations regarding environmental pollution, as evidenced by 123 respondents in Figure 4, which aligns them to be key to minimizing environmental pollution. PPPs are vital to this research, as reflected in the Casady et al. article "Public-Private Partnerships for low carbon, climate-resilient infrastructure." The article explains that PPPs are increasing globally and are used to provide climate mitigation and intervention, a major factor of environmental pollution (Casady et al., 2024).

CONCLUSION

Environmental pollution is one of Liberia's leading causes of climate change, putting people at risk of indoor and outdoor air pollution, which is primarily sourced from waste and particulate matter. The increase in health expenses is a key economic impact of environmental pollution, as shown in Figure 2. People living in poverty and children are the most vulnerable population to environmental pollution, as indicated in Figure 3. Practical strategies to minimize environmental pollution's effects include using biodegradable products and buying energy-effective appliances, as in Table 5. Establishing public-private partnerships, using Liberia's Public health Laws, and treating waste as a resource are among Liberia's best policies for minimizing environmental pollution.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Climate change is one of the major contributing factors to environmental pollution. The study recommends using eco-friendly products and energy-efficient appliances. Additionally, it proposes public-private partnerships for municipal solid waste management and the proper application of Liberia's Public health Laws

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HOW TO CITE: Dave Wuo Kehnel Jr.*, Effects of Environmental Pollution in Liberia: A Case Study of Montserrado (Republic of Liberia), *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (5), 177-187.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15346078>